

**STRUCTURE AND PRINCIPLES OF OPERATION OF MODERN
ENERGY STORAGE DEVICES**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes modern energy storage devices that can be used in power systems and conducts scientific and practical analysis of their application. Technical and economic performance of several energy storage devices is analyzed. A general analysis of energy storage devices that can be used in various energy production processes is conducted, and their main advantages and disadvantages are described in detail. Mathematical analyzes were performed based on the characteristics of each energy storage device.

Keywords: *Energy backup devices, mechanical energy storage, thermal energy storage, chemical energy storage, electromagnetic energy storage, Flywheel.*

Due to the current shortage of conventional energy sources around the world, the demand for energy storage devices is growing, which, of course, puts several priorities before energy storage devices or stations. First of all, today's era requires increasing the efficiency of energy storage devices and the modernization of modern environmentally friendly energy storage devices. There are two types of energy storage devices: traditional energy storage devices and modern energy storage devices. By traditional energy storage devices, we mean mainly chemical accumulation stations and hydroaccumulation stations. Modern energy storage devices can include mainly mechanical energy storage devices. Mechanical energy storage devices are also divided into kinetic energy storage devices and potential energy storage devices, depending on the type of energy. At present, the amount of energy consumed per unit of output in the Republic of Uzbekistan is much higher,

which requires the need to work on improving alternative energy storage devices. Given the scarcity of water facilities in most parts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is possible to achieve high efficiency using mechanical energy storage devices, especially for small consumers.

Modern energy storage devices can be divided into four main groups, depending on the type of energy.

Figure 1.Types of modern energy storage.

Modern Mechanical Energy Storage Devices.

Simple structures of modern mechanical energy storage devices have been used for many years, and today such devices are being improved. Today, such devices make up two major parts called potential and kinetic energy storage devices. In such devices, the stored energy can be converted into mechanical or electrical energy through additional devices. There are several types of modern mechanical energy storage devices:

Figure 2.Modern types of mechanical energy storage.

Potential energy storage devices: Potential energy, as defined, is a type of energy that is part of the energy of a particular moving or stationary body. If the body is at rest, then the total energy of the body is potential energy. Potential energy is the energy expended or released when moving an object at a certain height.

$$E_{mech} = E_{pot} + E_{kin} = mgh + \frac{mv^2}{2}$$

If an object is raised to a height h , this energy is called potential energy, and it is possible to obtain electrical or mechanical energy from this energy, but the specific energy of such devices is relatively less. The main advantage of potential energy storage devices is their long-term storage of stored energy. Potential types of energy storage may include compressed or elongated springs and tires, high-pressure compressed gases, and equipment used in hydroelectric power plants.

The energy obtained from elastic materials is equal to, if the mechanical system is not affected by additional forces other than the external environment.

$$E_{mech} = E_{pot} + E_{kin} = mgh + \frac{mv^2}{2}$$

σ - mechanical stress, ε - relative deformation, Y - Yung module.

The energy stored in elastic bodies is directly proportional to the square of absolute elongation and the virulence of the material.

$$E = \frac{1}{2}k\Delta x^2 \text{ (J)}$$

The energy stored in elastic materials can be converted into potential or kinetic energy. Due to the fact that the energy obtained from such devices has a fading property, it can be used in stop devices to transfer the amount of energy evenly. In such devices, the energy value is mainly estimated by the moment in the elastic body, and the following equation is used to estimate the moment in the elastic body.

$$T = \frac{\pi Ebt^3}{6L} \theta$$

There are E - the modulus of elasticity (MPa), L -the length of the package (mm), b - the width of the package (mm), t - the thickness of the package (mm), and θ - the angle of inclination.

Modern types of kinetic energy storage devices.

Today, modern kinetic energy storage devices are basically rotating disk energy, and such devices are called Flywheel. The worldwide use of Flywheel is growing, mainly due to the high environmental friendliness and power efficiency of these devices, the lack of periodic maintenance, long service life and, of course, high efficiency (around 83%). One of the main disadvantages of these energy storage devices is the high capital cost compared to other energy storage systems (\$ 4800 / kWh). However, operating and maintenance costs are low (\$ 19 kWh), and the temperature sensitivity to friction and other forces is significantly lower, due to the fact that the working part of the device is located in a vacuum. A modern Flywheel must be made of lightweight and durable devices for high-speed rotation. The main disadvantage of previous generations of these devices was the low speed of rotation of their steel part. With the use of modern materials, the rotation speed can be increased up to ten times. The rotating part of the flyweel must be made of durable materials with high strength.

Depending on the field of application, Flyweeh energy storage devices can also be used with low-speed and low-speed designs. Such devices can be made mainly of heavier materials. These devices use mechanical and magnetic bearings. These energy storage devices can be up to five times cheaper than high-speed energy storage devices. One of the safety considerations that must be taken into account when backing up energy through flywheel storage devices is that when these devices are energized, the rotor speed increases and it is recommended to back up the energy to the strength limit of the material. The energy stored in the flywheel energy storage device is determined as follows.

$$E_{FW} = \frac{1}{2} I \cdot \omega^2;$$

There are E - the stored kinetic energy, I - the moment of inertia, $\bar{\omega}$ - the angular velocity of the rotor. From this equation, we can see that in order to store more energy, it is necessary to increase the rotational speed or inertia of the rotating disk.

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